

Onboard UAV State Estimation and Trajectory Prediction Using Multi-task Reservoir Computing

Nicolas Souli, Panayiotis Kardaras, Yiannis Grigoriou, Panayiotis Kolios, and Georgios Ellinas

Abstract—The rapid advancements in unmanned aerial vehicle (UAV) technology have led to their use in different applications, ranging from critical infrastructure monitoring and search-and-rescue to remote sensing. However, UAV operations are easily affected by environmental conditions and sensor malfunctions that lead to the need for an efficient, accurate, and trustworthy state identification and trajectory prediction framework. This work proposes an innovative real-time UAV system with the two-fold objective of state identification and trajectory prediction, employing a lightweight multi-task learning framework based on reservoir computing (RC) network architecture to achieve reliable and robust UAV operations. Specifically, custom multi-task models are designed and fine-tuned to obtain multi-modal sequential data (related to drone movement) by exploiting the ability of shared feature learning in an RC-based network architecture to accurately achieve and enhance real-time and simultaneous drone state classification and trajectory prediction. A real-world dataset is also created to train and evaluate the proposed multi-task model, encompassing drone movements recorded during numerous outdoor experiments. Finally, a UAV prototype system is implemented and extensively tested in a real-world environment to demonstrate its enhanced performance in trajectory prediction and drone state identification compared to existing methods.

I. INTRODUCTION

Unmanned aerial vehicles have been extensively integrated into the national airspace across different applications (e.g., remote sensing, disaster management, civil infrastructure inspection, wireless communication coverage, and critical infrastructure security) due to their ease of use, low-cost hardware, and versatility [1]. Nevertheless, to assure safety and meet the strict time, security, and reliability requirements during critical UAV operations such as search-and-rescue and disaster management, robust, efficient, and trustworthy flight monitoring mechanisms in cases of abnormal behavior and sensor malfunctions are becoming a necessity [2], [3], and failure to adhere to them can lead to dire consequences [4]. This is the case, as accurate prediction of future trajectories and classification of UAV states can provide UAV operators with improved real-time situational awareness and enhanced

security measures to mitigate hazards associated with abnormal flight behaviors [4], [5].

Current research efforts have primarily focused on single-objective frameworks for either state identification or trajectory prediction, employing long short-term memory (LSTM) networks and recurrent neural networks (RNN). However, these methods are unable to effectively capture temporal dependencies in the data over prolonged time horizons [6], [7]. To address this issue, Transformer neural networks that leverage self-attention mechanisms have demonstrated better performance in sequential data processing [8] and outperform RNNs and LSTM networks in tasks involving natural language processing and time series prediction [9]. Also, the Reservoir computing (RC) network is a type of recurrent network that reduces computational complexity, while also providing improved results for time series forecasting applications [10]. Despite the recent advancements in Transformer- and RC-based networks, their application in autonomous drone navigation remains largely unexplored.

This work extends our Transformer-based multi-task learning framework (MELF-ST) [11], used to compute joint UAV state identification and trajectory prediction from multi-modal input data. MELF-ST aimed to optimize the performance of both tasks by leveraging the UAV’s sensor data and historical trajectory information. In contrast, this work proposes a real-time system for UAV state identification and trajectory prediction that employs a lightweight RC architecture (MT-RES) on an onboard embedded processing unit, that accomplishes its dual objective while also enhancing both operational efficiency and inference accuracy. Specifically, the main contributions of this work are as follows:

- Design of a custom RC-based innovative multi-task learning model that achieves the two-fold objective of classification and trajectory prediction, employing multi-modal time-series data from various onboard UAV sensors. Compared to the state of the art, the proposed model achieves reduced training time and improved accuracy with low computational requirements.
- Selection of optimized configuration parameters to enhance both the classification and 3D trajectory prediction accuracy of the model.
- Implementation of a sliding window technique to collect the historical data of the UAV’s past states to provide robustness and effectiveness of the proposed solution for real-time inference.
- Creation of a real-world dataset that extends previously published datasets (Dataset-1 [12] and Dataset-2 [13]) by incorporating z-axis transitions and UAV flights with more complex paths having longer range and duration.
- Design of a lightweight model of the proposed learning

N. Souli, P. Kardaras, Y. Grigoriou and G. Ellinas are with the Department of Electrical and Computer Engineering and the KIOS Research and Innovation Center of Excellence, University of Cyprus, Nicosia, Cyprus. P. Kolios is with the Department of Computer Science and the KIOS Research and Innovation Center of Excellence, University of Cyprus. Emails: {nsouli02, kardaras.panagiotis, grigoriou.yiannis, pkolios, gellinas}@ucy.ac.cy

This work was partially supported by the Border Management and Visa Policy Instrument (BMVI), co-financed by the European Union and the Republic of Cyprus (BMVI/2021-2022/SA/1.2.1/015) (project REACTION) and by the European Union’s Horizon Europe research and innovation program under grant agreement No 101187121 (EUSOME). It was also partially supported from the Republic of Cyprus through the Deputy Ministry of Research, Innovation and Digital Policy.

architecture and implementation of a prototype system on a UAV based on ROS, SQL databases, RC, and multi-task learning and thorough testing in real-world outdoor experiments to assess its performance in terms of real-time classification and 3D trajectory prediction.

In the rest of the paper, Sec. II presents related work while Secs. III and IV detail the proposed MT-RES system and algorithm, respectively. Section V showcases the proposed system’s performance evaluation and Sec. VI summarizes the key findings and outlines future research directions.

II. RELATED WORK

Existing research on UAV state identification has primarily relied on conventional methods such as simultaneous localization and mapping (SLAM) [14] and visual-inertial odometry (VIO) [15] for real-time estimation of a UAV’s position and orientation. Even though these techniques are effective for specific scenarios, their high computational requirements and decreased accuracy in complex outdoor environments have led to the investigation of alternative approaches [16], such as a deep learning technique for state estimation with the employment of CNN-based architecture [17], that demonstrated reliable and accurate results in various environments.

Furthermore, existing UAV trajectory prediction works mainly focused on achieving safe and efficient navigation, conventionally involving the use of model-based algorithms (e.g., Kalman filters) [18]. Also, recent research advancements in deep learning methods have introduced promising data-driven methods for trajectory prediction. However, RNN and LSTM methods encounter significant challenges in capturing long-range and long-term dependencies within sequential data, an area where Transformer- and Reservoir-based models can achieve higher performance [19].

Specifically, the Transformer model, introduced in [8], is utilized for sequence-to-sequence prediction tasks (such as language processing) because of its capability to handle long-term dependencies in sequential data. In [20], a spatial-temporal graph attention transformer for trajectory prediction in autonomous driving was proposed. The model was trained based on a specific trajectory dataset and demonstrated accurate results for trajectory prediction; however, its performance deteriorated when applied in different driving conditions or locations. Similarly, in [21] a lane transformer model was employed for trajectory prediction in autonomous driving, again demonstrating performance degradation over longer prediction horizons, leading to the need for a better strategy to handle long-term prediction effects.

Only a small number of works have employed Reservoir-based models to achieve short-term or long-term prediction tasks. For example, the work in [22] proposed an RC-based technique to learn the forward dynamics of industrial manipulators using only sensor data. Additionally, in [10], an RC-based technique for drone trajectory prediction was investigated, demonstrating high prediction accuracy. Nevertheless, that architecture was only evaluated in controlled environments, using only smooth and noise-free trajectories and neglecting changes in the altitude.

Additionally, multi-task learning (MTL), first introduced in [23], is a method where a model is trained to handle

multiple tasks simultaneously by utilizing shared information across related tasks. This technique can increase model performance, enhance generalization, and provide overfitting mitigation [24]. MTL can be implemented using techniques such as hard/soft parameter sharing and task-specific attention [24], [25], [26]. In the field of autonomous vehicles, such as UAVs, multi-task learning (MTL) provides a framework for simultaneously learning multiple tasks (e.g., object detection, state identification, and trajectory prediction) [27], [28]. By sharing information across these related tasks, MTL mitigates the need for large amounts of labeled data, which is often a challenge in UAV applications.

Even though transformer- and reservoir-based models demonstrate accurate 2D trajectory prediction or classification, further exploration is required for multi-task learning. Currently, no Reservoir-based models have focused on multi-task trajectory and classification prediction for UAV applications. Therefore, the proposed work complements the aforementioned research by proposing a real-time multi-task system for trajectory prediction and UAV state identification by employing an onboard lightweight RC model in real-world outdoor environments (3D space).

III. SYSTEM OVERVIEW

A. Background on RC Models

The RC architecture allows the design of a dynamical model that captures the temporal patterns and maps the input (sequential) data $\mathbf{u}(t)$ to high-dimensional complex patterns $\mathbf{x}(t)$ and then computes the desired output $\mathbf{y}(t)$ [29]. RC-based networks differ from conventional RNN and LSTM networks as they can approximate complex dynamical systems with low computational cost. These networks are structured into three main components: a) an encoder layer that projects the input data into a heterogeneous high-dimensional space; b) a reservoir layer, which comprises a diverse set of dynamic elements that capture the high-dimensional characteristics of the input features; and c) a decoder layer, defined as readout, that converts these high-dimensional features back into a low-dimensional representation that aligns with the desired output [10]. It is important to note that in the proposed scheme the reservoir layer consists of a large, randomly connected recurrent network with fixed nodes. In this architecture, only the readout layer undergoes training, which results in a more rapid training process.

B. MT-RES Framework

The proposed MT-RES framework (Fig. 1) consists of four main components, namely the encoder layer, reservoir, readout layer, and a feed-forward network, which is followed by separate output branches for the trajectory prediction and state classification tasks. The model’s input data matrix $\mathbf{u}(t)$ ($\mathbf{u}(t) \in \mathbb{R}^n$ with \mathbb{R} denoting the real number space and n the input data dimensionality) includes the drone’s onboard sensor data (GNSS coordinates, altitude, ground speed and angular velocity, ground acceleration, orientation, and power consumption) along with the weather station’s measurements (wind speed and wind direction).

Initially, $\mathbf{u}(t)$ is transformed into a high-dimensional state through a fixed, randomly initialized input weight matrix \mathbf{M}_{in} . The data are then converted using $\mathbf{x}(t) = \tanh(\mathbf{M}_{in} \cdot$

Fig. 1: MT-RES model framework.

$\mathbf{u}(t) + \mathbf{M}_{\text{res}} \cdot \mathbf{x}(t-1)$), where $\mathbf{x}(t)$ represents the state of the reservoir at time t , \mathbf{M}_{res} is the reservoir weight matrix, defining the internal connections within the reservoir, and \tanh is the activation function introducing non-linearity. This allows $\mathbf{u}(t)$ to interact with the reservoir's internal states.

The reservoir processing consists of N neurons, each interacting with its neighboring nodes through fixed weights (\mathbf{M}_{res}). The internal dynamics of the reservoir capture the temporal patterns of the input sequence. The update of the reservoir state at each time step is computed by $\mathbf{x}(t) = (1 - \alpha)\mathbf{x}(t-1) + \alpha \tanh(\mathbf{M}_{\text{res}} \cdot \mathbf{x}(t-1) + \mathbf{M}_{\text{in}} \cdot \mathbf{u}(t))$, where α is the leak rate, controlling the memory of the reservoir and the rate at which the reservoir state changes and r is the reservoir's state dimensionality ($\mathbf{x}(t) \in \mathbb{R}^r$).

Afterwards, the readout layer maps the high-dimensional reservoir states to the desired output. Only the weights of the readout layer \mathbf{M}_{out} are trained, using linear regression to minimize the error between predicted outputs $\hat{\mathbf{y}}(t)$ and actual outputs $\mathbf{y}(t)$ (with $\mathbf{y}(t) \in \mathbb{R}^n$) by using $\hat{\mathbf{y}}(t) = \mathbf{M}_{\text{out}} \cdot \mathbf{x}(t)$. The optimal readout weights \mathbf{M}_{out} are then computed by solving the ridge regression problem $\mathbf{M}_{\text{out}} = \arg \min_{\mathbf{M}} \sum_t \|\mathbf{y}(t) - \mathbf{M} \cdot \mathbf{x}(t)\|^2 + \lambda \|\mathbf{M}\|^2$, where λ is the regularization parameter to prevent overfitting.

The MT-RES *build model* function is used to create the proposed model, using parameters such as the input shape, reservoir nodes, spectral radius, leak rate, forecasting window, and feed-forward dimensions. The function builds two parallel branches aimed at achieving both trajectory prediction and multi-label classification. These branches consist of a sequence of reservoir blocks, with the number of layers determined by the specified *number of Reservoir blocks*. Then, at each branch, *TimeDistributed Dense* layers are employed, utilizing *linear* activation for trajectory prediction and *sigmoid* activation for state identification (multi-label classification). The outputs are then further processed to match the forecast horizon (*HS*).

After model assembly, an Adam optimizer is used along with a hybrid loss function that combines the *mean squared error (MSE)* for trajectory prediction with *binary cross-entropy* for state identification, with equal weights assigned to both MT-RES components. The framework also incorporates a *ModelCheckpoint* callback to save the best-performing model during training, and an *EarlyStopping* callback to stop training if the validation loss for trajectory prediction does

not improve over a predefined number of epochs.

To summarize, a real-time multi-task system for trajectory prediction and state identification is proposed, applied onboard a UAV, that uses a custom ROS framework to collect the UAV's onboard sensor data, combined with an SQL database to save the RC-based architecture's output that is then displayed on a web-based platform for monitoring purposes (Fig. 2). In cases of abnormal flight behavior or sensor malfunction the UAV pilot, using the MT-RES output, is able to intervene to mitigate serious hazards.

Fig. 2: System overview.

IV. MT-RES ALGORITHM

The MT-RES framework, as delineated in Alg. 1, processes the acquired flight data through a series of steps, aiming at drone trajectory forecasting and current state identification. The data are systematically extracted, processed, and organized into input and output sets, including multi-classification records. Key parameters, such as input size (*IS*), window size (*WS*), and *HS*, are established and applied in an overlapping time-based sliding window operation. The data undergo a 3D-to-2D transformation, followed by ONNX conversion for enhanced prediction speed. After reverting to 3D, the data are split into training, validation, and testing sets. The multi-task learning model is then constructed with specified inputs/outputs and hyperparameters, such as batch size, epochs, number of classes, head size, and learning rate. The model is then compiled and its performance is assessed.

The data partitioning procedure involves subscribing to a ROS topic to retrieve UAV input features, incorporating conditional checks to determine if the UAV has landed concluding its mission. If the mission is not finished, the procedure analyzes and reconstructs UAV flight records, storing the filtered information in a database. The code initializes variables and employs loops and conditional statements to update entries and control the execution flow based on predefined requirements. This process includes determining the necessity for labeling or executing the model to obtain the required outputs. Each timestamp is labeled with the corresponding flight mode, and multi-label classifications are assigned to capture all relevant attributes, with the records systematically stored in the database for future retrieval and analysis. Finally, the Haversine formula [30] is used to

compute distances (in meters), calculating the error as the Euclidean distance between actual and predicted positions.

Algorithm 1 MT-RES Framework

Input: Collected UAV flight dataset

```

1: procedure (Building and Training of the model)
2:   Define and initialize model parameters ( $HS$ , reservoir units, batch
   size, number of heads, head size, number of classes, number of
   transformer blocks, feed-forward dimensions, leak rate, spectral radius)
3:   Reshape and normalize input data
4:   Convert to ONNX for faster inference time
5:   Compile, train, and evaluate the model
6:   Compute and adjust the ridge weights
7: end procedure
8: procedure (Data Partitioning, Input Size and Sliding Window)
9:   Retrieve UAV input features by subscribing to a ROS topic
10:  if Drone_landed then
11:    Mission finished. No more actions needed
12:  else
13:    Analyze and reconstruct UAV flight records with classification
14:    Save the filtered information in database
15:  end if
16:  Initialize  $IS$ ,  $WS$ 
17:  while  $IS \bmod WS \neq 0$  do  $\rightarrow$  Update  $IS$  entries
18:  end while
19:  if  $IS \bmod WS = 0$  then  $\rightarrow$  goto Line 26
20:  end if
21:  while  $IS \bmod (2WS) \neq 0$  do  $\rightarrow$  goto Line 17
22:  end while
23:  if  $IS \bmod (2WS) = 0$  then  $\rightarrow$  goto Line 31
24:  end if
25: end procedure
26: procedure (Labelling)
27:   Label each timestamp with the appropriate flight mode
28:   Assign multi-label classifications
29:   Save the labeled data in database
30: end procedure
31: procedure (Model Outputs)
32:   Compute classification and trajectory prediction (with RC)
33:   Calculate Haversine and Euclidean Distances and save in database
34: end procedure

```

Output: Trajectory estimation and current state identification results

V. PERFORMANCE EVALUATION

A. Hardware Configuration

The DJI Matrice 300 RTK [31] is the main platform for data collection, chosen for its compatibility with onboard development kits. The NVIDIA Jetson Xavier NX serves as the embedded computing device for running the developed software. Utilizing the Onboard Software Development Kit (OSDK), the Jetson Xavier NX enables real-time access and processing of data from the drone’s sensors and flight controller. Furthermore, OSDK-ROS is employed to retrieve sensor data, with corresponding topics made available for subscription by the software running on the Jetson. The proposed system’s hardware configuration is depicted in Fig. 3.

B. Data Acquisition and Annotation

Data acquisition missions include five distinct patterns (triangular, circular, rectangular, linear, and multi-dimensional as illustrated in Fig. 4). Each mission is configured as a waypoint flight path, allowing customization of the altitude, speed, and turning angle. The resulting dataset (Dataset-3 [32]) comprises 3D spatial flight data logged at a frequency of 10 Hz, totaling 276,057 entries. To ensure data consistency, identical parameters are applied across all missions. Specifically, the dataset includes 20 flights, with each flight

Fig. 3: (a) DJI M300, (b) NVIDIA Jetson, (c) OSDK module.

path repeated several times, resulting in approximately 30 minutes of flight time per mission. Also, the dataset is divided into 65% for training, 20% for validation, and 15% for testing purposes. The testing set is specifically developed to enable a thorough assessment by incorporating the various dataset flight-path trajectories (such as triangular, circular, rectangular, linear, and multi-dimensional mission paths), as well as the introduction of additional numerous manual flight-paths performed during outdoor experiments. This allows the proposed framework to be evaluated using a testing set that is based on real-world outdoor scenarios, with performance evaluation metrics that include the total average Euclidean error for trajectory prediction and state estimation accuracy. To further validate the robustness and adaptability of this framework, 20 real-world outdoor experiments are conducted on complex UAV flight paths. The presented total average Euclidean error encompasses both the predefined paths in the dataset and additional manual flight paths. The data are organized as time-series, with each flight uniquely identified by a flight number and its corresponding timestamp.

The dataset contains labels for various operational states of the UAV, including IDLE-HOVER, ASCEND, TURN, HMSL (horizontal straight line), and DESCEND, that can be then used to classify its current activity, making it applicable for trajectory prediction in MTL models.

In terms of the dataset sensor specifications, wind speed is measured using an onboard weather station [33], providing airspeed in m/s, while the wind angle is collected as the angle of air flowing through the sensor relative to the north (in degrees). Power consumption information includes the battery voltage (in volts) and the battery current (in amperes). The UAV’s position is acquired in both the horizontal plane, through the longitude and latitude coordinates (x , y), and the vertical axis (z), providing the altitude relative to sea level (in meters). Additionally, orientation data are gathered in quaternions, representing the UAV’s orientation in terms of roll, pitch, and yaw. Velocity components (v_x , v_y , v_z) in m/s and angular velocity (av_x , av_y , av_z) in rad/s are also monitored. The system also measures linear acceleration (a_x , a_y , a_z) in m/s^2 and payload mass (in grams).

Fig. 4: Data acquisition missions.

C. Experimental Results

This section details the experimental results, assessing the location prediction performance of MT-RES against ground truth (GT) values obtained from the UAV’s GPS+RTK sensors, and evaluating its state identification accuracy by comparing the predicted with the actual UAV states in multiple field experiments of 3D complex flight paths.

To assess the average performance of MT-RES and also compare it with our previously developed MELF-ST framework based on Transformer networks [11], a fine-tuning procedure is initially conducted to adjust the hyperparameters of both models to achieve the best possible results. At first, the hyperparameter search space for both MT-RES and MELF-ST is defined, followed by a strategy to randomly search through all 400 possible configurations. All configurations are evaluated and validated based on Dataset-3 to select the optimized model configuration. For MELF-ST, the hyperparameter search space includes head size (hs), number of heads (nh), feed-forward dimensions (ff_{dim}), number of transformer blocks (tb), and batch size (bs), while for MT-RES it includes reservoir nodes ($nodes$), leak rate (lr), and spectral radius (sr). Following the fine-tuning procedure, the top-5 performing models (out of 400 configurations) for both MT-RES and MELF-ST are presented in Fig. 5. Table I also tabulates the location estimation accuracy for the top-performing models (for both MT-RES and MELF-ST) when numerous outdoor field experiments are conducted, demon-

strating that location estimation performance decreases with increasing prediction time-step (t). Nevertheless, it also shows that MT-RES provides accurate location estimates, with an average Euclidean distance error of less than 2.7m (when $HS=3$), significantly outperforming MELF-ST, that demonstrates an average error of 4.68m.

Fig. 5: Top-5 performing models: (a) MT-RES, (b) MELF-ST.

TABLE I: Average Euclidean error for trajectory prediction.

All testing flights	Prediction time (s)	Euclidean error (m)	Euclidean error (m)
		MT-RES $nodes=5000, lr=0.1, sr=0.8, bs=32$	MELF-ST $hs=256, nh=4, ff_{dim}=1024, tb=2, bs=48$
	t+1	2.57	4.35
	t+2	2.68	4.42
	t+3	2.86	4.63

Further, Fig. 6 presents the cumulative distribution function (CDF) of the error for trajectory estimation, comparing MT-RES with MELF-ST when $HS=3$ and $WS=90$. The results illustrate that MT-RES achieves accurate location estimation performance with small mean prediction error and error variability. Specifically, for MT-RES, the 1-, 2-, and 3-second look-ahead predictions exhibit errors below 4.7, 5, and 5.3m, respectively, for 90% of the time (Fig. 6(a)), whereas for MELF-ST they exhibit errors of 7.9, 8.1, and 8.9m, respectively, for 90% of the time (Fig. 6(b)).

TABLE II: Average Euclidean distance error for trajectory prediction using different WS parameter values.

All testing flights MT-RES	Prediction time (s)	Euclidean error (m)	Euclidean error (m)	Euclidean error (m)
		$WS=30$	$WS=60$	$WS=90$
	t+1	3.76	2.99	2.57
	t+2	3.81	3.05	2.68
	t+3	3.902	3.34	2.86

Fig. 6: Average CDF error for predicted trajectories at $t+1$, $t+2$, and $t+3$. (a) MT-RES and (b) MELF-ST.

In terms of the sliding window size, Table II illustrates that when WS increases, the performance of MT-RES improves (i.e., the average Euclidean distance error decreases). This occurs because incorporating more information about the drone’s previous locations enables the trajectory prediction to achieve a lower estimation error (i.e., less than 2.57m for the 1-second look-ahead horizon).

Figure 7 also demonstrates that the overall trajectory prediction performance of the MT-RES model deteriorates (even for the short-term prediction steps) when a 9-second look-ahead horizon is used. This occurs mainly due to the increased complexity induced by forecasting for the 9-second horizon, that steers the model to focus on minimizing the long-term error, highlighting a clear trade-off between the HS value and trajectory prediction accuracy. Nevertheless, despite the deterioration in MT-RES performance, MT-RES still outperforms MELF-ST in terms of trajectory prediction.

It is important to note that utilizing historical information with a WS value greater than 90 does not lead to significant improvement in the system’s performance, as historical data beyond the 9-second horizon tend to have a weaker correlation with future states due to the rapidly changing nature of the environment. This behavior is evident in Fig. 8, that presents the trajectory prediction of a look-ahead horizon of 9-seconds with WS values of 180.

Moreover, the deviations between the GT and predicted trajectories when utilizing MT-RES and MELF-ST (with $WS=90$, $HS=30$, and the use of optimal model parameters of Table I), are depicted in Fig. 9, showcasing that the estimated trajectory is comparable to the GT (even when the UAV agent follows a non-linear flight path). In particular, MT-RES achieves average Euclidean distance errors of 2.57m, 2.68m, and 2.86m for look-ahead horizons of 1-, 2-, and 3-sec, respectively.

The MT-RES model has also been evaluated in comparison to traditional techniques such as Kalman filter and LSTM networks, using performance metrics such as accuracy and latency. In real-world UAV navigation scenarios, the EKF is typically employed as the baseline for trajectory forecasting due to its ability to effectively integrate the UAV state dynamics with various sensor data types. However, during prolonged outdoor UAV flights, where sensor measurement noise, dynamic system uncertainties, and deviations from

Fig. 7: Average Euclidean error for predicted trajectories ($t+1$ to $t+9$ horizon, $WS=90$). (a) MT-RES, (b) MELF-ST.

Fig. 8: Average Euclidean error for predicted trajectories ($t+1$ to $t+9$ horizon, $WS=180$): (a) MT-RES, (b) MELF-ST.

initial conditions are present, the trajectory prediction accuracy deteriorates (as shown in Table III and further discussed in [34], [35]). Therefore, employing data-driven forecasting approaches, such as LSTM-, Transformer-, and Reservoir-based models [11], [28], leads to higher trajectory prediction accuracy. Additionally, these approaches allow estimating the UAV’s state beyond the 1-second look-ahead horizon (e.g.,

Fig. 9: MT-RES trajectory prediction results (3D flight path) compared to MELF-ST and the ground truth (GPS+RTK).

1-, 2-, or 3-second look-ahead horizons) during prolonged outdoor UAV operations. While data-driven methods achieve higher trajectory prediction accuracy and an improved UAV state estimation over extended forecast horizons, EKF techniques outperform these approaches in real-time latency and computational efficiency due to their minimal computational requirements utilized to achieve trajectory prediction for the 1-second look-ahead horizon. However, employing the proposed MT-RES framework results in a mean iteration time of 0.39s, which is comparable to the mean iteration time of 0.3s for conventional EKF-based methods [36] and notably better than the 0.8s and 0.7s achieved for LSTM- and Transformer-based methods, respectively. It should be noted that, to obtain these results, the ONNX framework [37] for model compression is employed on the Jetson Xavier NX onboard processing unit and tested in various outdoor experiments.

TABLE III: Mean Euclidean error (meters) of selected techniques.

#	GNSS+IMU	INS	EKF	LSTM	MELF-ST	MT-RES	Mean Euclidean error (m)
1	x						1.5
2		x					21
3		x	x				7.7
4				x			5.5
5					x		4.35
6						x	2.57

Regarding state identification, multi-label classification is performed within Dataset-3, distinguishing between five distinct classes (IDLE-HOVER, ASCEND, TURN, HMSL, and DESCEND). To evaluate the multi-label classification performance of the proposed MT-RES framework, the Precision, Recall, and F1-score metrics [38] are computed and presented in Table IV. Results obtained demonstrate that MT-RES provides better classification accuracy when compared to MELF-ST for the IDLE-HOVER, ASCEND, and HMSL classes, with F1-scores 0.76, 0.773, and 0.86, respectively (compared to 0.75, 0.742, and 0.845 values for MELF-ST). Even though there is room for improvement for the TURN and DESCEND classes, where F1-scores of 0.6745 and 0.676 are achieved, MT-RES again demonstrates better classification performance for the TURN and DESCEND classes compared to MELF-ST, which recorded F1-scores of 0.5898 and 0.65, respectively. Micro- and macro-average metrics for Precision, Recall, and F1-score are also computed (Table V), demonstrating that the micro-average metrics are higher than the macro-ones, highlighting the overall increased performance of the model.

Finally, CPU, GPU, RAM, and power consumption is illustrated in Fig. 10 (with 100% power consumption corre-

TABLE IV: MT-RES Class-wise metrics.

Class	Precision	Recall	F1-score
	WS 30/60/90	WS 30/60/90	WS 30/60/90
IDLE-HOVER	0.77/0.782/0.794	0.701/0.712/0.727	0.723/0.755/0.76
ASCEND	0.82/0.839/0.842	0.7/0.711/0.712	0.754/0.769/0.773
TURN	0.81/0.821/0.838	0.551/0.562/0.564	0.662/0.673/0.6745
HMSL	0.792/0.802/0.814	0.897/0.906/0.91	0.824/0.853/0.86
DESCEND	0.563/0.576/0.58	0.796/0.8/0.813	0.653/0.659/0.676

TABLE V: MT-RES Average metrics.

Metric	Micro-average	Macro-average
	WS 30/60/90	WS 30/60/90
Precision	0.792/0.795/0.8	0.765/0.771/0.773
Recall	0.795/0.797/0.799	0.733/0.739/0.746
F1-score	0.792/0.797/0.7996	0.722/0.732/0.748

sponding to the 20W maximum power for the Jetson device), demonstrating the proposed system’s capability to function as an onboard, lightweight, real-time UAV solution capable of performing trajectory prediction and state identification. Note that spikes are observed when the MT-RES is in use, indicating an overall onboard resource allocation below 50%.

Fig. 10: Onboard resource allocation for MT-RES.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

This work proposes a real-time multi-task learning system using an RC network (MT-RES) that is applied onboard a UAV and achieves both drone state identification and trajectory prediction. The proposed system leverages the Reservoir-based model’s capability to process sequential data, combined with a sliding window technique that utilizes historical data, to accurately identify the drone’s current state and predict its future trajectory. A custom dataset is also developed to train and fine-tune the proposed framework, incorporating complex trajectories with varying altitudes. An extensive evaluation of the proposed onboard system, conducted through real-world outdoor experiments, demonstrates its ability to improve the overall safety and efficiency of UAV-based operations (video of the experiments at https://ucy-my.sharepoint.com/:v:/g/personal/nsouli02_ucy_ac_cy/Exp1Lpgq6GFDuRNzcxLhtKkBWfSrGJUswRQR8EB7FWzeeQ). Future research includes incorporating additional tasks into the MT-RES model, utilizing vision sensor modalities, and extending Dataset-3 to enhance the system’s performance.

REFERENCES

- [1] H. Shakhatreh, A. H. Sawalmeh, A. Al-Fuqaha, Z. Dou, E. Almaita, I. Khalil, N. S. Othman, A. Khreishah, and M. Guizani, "Unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs): A survey on civil applications and key research challenges," *IEEE Access*, vol. 7, pp. 48 572–48 634, 2019.
- [2] C. Xu, X. Liao, J. Tan, H. Ye, and H. Lu, "Recent research progress of unmanned aerial vehicle regulation policies and technologies in urban low altitude," *IEEE Access*, vol. 8, pp. 74 175–74 194, 2020.
- [3] M. Corbetta, P. Banerjee, W. Okolo, G. Gorospe, and D. G. Luchinsky, "Real-time UAV trajectory prediction for safety monitoring in low-altitude airspace," in *Proc. AIAA Aviation Forum*, 2019.
- [4] S. Waharte and N. Trigoni, "Supporting search and rescue operations with UAVs," in *Proc. IEEE International Conference on Emerging Security Technologies (EST)*, 2010, pp. 142–147.
- [5] Y. Huang, J. Du, Z. Yang, Z. Zhou, L. Zhang, and H. Chen, "A survey on trajectory-prediction methods for autonomous driving," *IEEE Transactions on Intelligent Vehicles*, vol. 7, no. 3, pp. 652–674, 2022.
- [6] P. Shu, C. Chen, B. Chen, K. Su, S. Chen, H. Liu, and F. Huang, "Trajectory prediction of UAV based on LSTM," in *Proc. 2nd International Conference on Big Data & Artificial Intelligence & Software Engineering (ICBASE)*, 2021, pp. 448–451.
- [7] K. Xiao, J. Zhao, Y. He, and S. Yu, "Trajectory prediction of UAV in smart city using recurrent neural networks," in *Proc. IEEE International Conference on Communications (ICC)*, 2019, pp. 1–6.
- [8] A. Vaswani, N. Shazeer, N. Parmar, J. Uszkoreit, L. Jones, A. N. Gomez, L. Kaiser, and I. Polosukhin, "Attention is all you need," in *Proc. 31st Conference on Neural Information Processing Systems*, 2017, pp. 1–11.
- [9] Q. Tong, J. Hu, Y. Chen, D. Guo, and X. Liu, "Long-term trajectory prediction model based on transformer," *IEEE Access*, vol. 11, pp. 143 695–143 703, 2023.
- [10] A. Perrusquía and W. Guo, "Reservoir computing for drone trajectory intent prediction: A physics informed approach," *IEEE Transactions on Cybernetics*, vol. 54, no. 9, pp. 4939–4948, 2024.
- [11] N. Souli, A. Palamas, T. Panayiotou, P. Kolios, and G. Ellinas, "A multi-task transformer architecture for drone state identification and trajectory prediction," in *Proc. IEEE 20th International Conference on Distributed Computing in Smart Systems and the Internet of Things (DCOSS-IoT)*, 2024, pp. 285–291.
- [12] T. A. Rodrigues, J. Patrikar, A. Choudhry, J. Feldgoise, V. Arcot, A. Gahlaut, S. Lau, B. Moon, B. Wagner, H. S. Matthews, S. Scherer, and C. Samaras, "In-flight positional and energy use data set of a DJI Matrice 100 quadcopter for small package delivery," *Scientific Data*, vol. 8, no. 155, pp. 1–8, 2021.
- [13] A. Palamas and P. Kolios, "Dataset-2: Dataset obtained from multi-modal sensor onboard the drone," 2023. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7643456>
- [14] H. Durrant-Whyte and T. Bailey, "Simultaneous localization and mapping: part I," *IEEE Robotics & Automation Magazine*, vol. 13, no. 2, pp. 99–110, 2006.
- [15] C. Forster, M. Pizzoli, and D. Scaramuzza, "SVO: Fast semi-direct monocular visual odometry," in *Proc. IEEE International Conference on Robotics and Automation (ICRA)*, 2014, pp. 15–22.
- [16] A. Kendall, M. Grimes, and R. Cipolla, "PoseNet: A convolutional network for real-time 6-DOF camera relocalization," in *Proc. IEEE International Conference on Computer Vision (ICCV)*, 2015, pp. 2938–2946.
- [17] A. Loquercio, A. I. Maqueda, C. R. Del-Blanco, and D. Scaramuzza, "DroNet: Learning to fly by driving," *IEEE Robotics & Automation Letters*, vol. 3, no. 2, pp. 1088–1095, 2018.
- [18] S. J. Julier and J. K. Uhlmann, "Unscented filtering and nonlinear estimation," *Proceedings of the IEEE*, vol. 92, no. 3, pp. 401–422, 2004.
- [19] Y. Bengio, P. Simard, and P. Frasconi, "Learning long-term dependencies with gradient descent is difficult," *IEEE Transactions on Neural Networks*, vol. 5, no. 2, pp. 157–166, 1994.
- [20] K. Zhang, X. Feng, L. Wu, and Z. He, "Trajectory prediction for autonomous driving using spatial-temporal graph attention transformer," *IEEE Transactions on Intelligent Transportation Systems*, vol. 23, no. 11, pp. 22 343–22 353, 2022.
- [21] Z. Wang, J. Guo, Z. Hu, H. Zhang, J. Zhang, and J. Pu, "Lane transformer: A high-efficiency trajectory prediction model," *IEEE Open Journal of Intelligent Transportation Systems*, vol. 4, pp. 2–13, 2023.
- [22] A. S. Polydoros and L. Nalpantidis, "A reservoir computing approach for learning forward dynamics of industrial manipulators," in *Proc. IEEE/RSJ International Conference on Intelligent Robots and Systems (IROS)*, 2016, pp. 612–618.
- [23] R. Caruana, "Multitask learning," *Machine Learning*, vol. 28, pp. 41–75, 1997.
- [24] S. Ruder, "An overview of multi-task learning in deep neural networks," *arXiv:1706.05098 [cs.LG]*, 2017.
- [25] R. Caruana, *Multitask Learning*. Springer, 1998.
- [26] X. Liu, P. He, W. Chen, and J. Gao, "Multi-task deep neural networks for natural language understanding," *arXiv:1901.11504 [cs.CL]*, 2019.
- [27] G. Verdon, M. Broughton, J. R. McClean, K. J. Sung, R. Babbush, Z. Jiang, H. Neven, and M. Mohseni, "Learning to learn with quantum neural networks via classical neural networks," *arXiv:1907.05415 [quant-ph]*, 2019.
- [28] A. Palamas, N. Souli, T. Panayiotou, P. Kolios, and G. Ellinas, "A multi-task learning framework for drone state identification and trajectory prediction," in *Proc. IEEE International Conference on Distributed Computing in Smart Systems and The Internet of Things (DCOSS-IoT)*, 2023, pp. 676–683.
- [29] M. Cucchi, S. Abreu, G. Ciccone, D. Brunner, and H. Kleemann, "Hands-on reservoir computing: a tutorial for practical implementation," *Neuromorphic Computing and Engineering*, vol. 2, no. 3, p. 032002, 2022.
- [30] E. Winarno, W. Hadikurniawati, and R. N. Rosso, "Location based service for presence system using Haversine method," in *Proc. International Conference on Innovative and Creative Information Technology (ICITech)*, 2017, pp. 1–4.
- [31] DJI, "Matrice 300 RTK DJI Enterprise," Available at <https://enterprise.dji.com/matrice-300/specs>.
- [32] Y. Grigoriou and N. Souli, "Dataset-3: Drone onboard multi-modal sensor dataset for complex outdoor scenarios," 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://zenodo.org/records/13682870>
- [33] UST, "TriSonica Mini Wind and Weather Sensor," Available at <https://www.unmannedsystemstechnology.com/company/licor/trisonica-mini-wind-and-weather-sensor/>.
- [34] A. Nemra and N. Aouf, "Robust INS/GPS sensor fusion for UAV localization using SDRE nonlinear filtering," *IEEE Sensors Journal*, vol. 10, no. 4, pp. 789–798, 2010.
- [35] J. Havlík and O. Straka, "Performance evaluation of iterated extended Kalman filter with variable step-length," *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*, vol. 659, no. 1, p. 012022, 2015.
- [36] Z. Wang, Y. Huang, Y. Zhang, G. Jia, and J. Chambers, "An improved Kalman filter with adaptive estimate of latency probability," *IEEE Transactions on Circuits and Systems II: Express Briefs*, vol. 67, no. 10, pp. 2259–2263, 2020.
- [37] F. Xu, "Faster scalable ML model deployment using ONNX and open source tools," in *Proc. IEEE Infrastructure Conference*, 2020.
- [38] F. P. Moreno, F. I. Rodríguez, V. F. G. Comendador, R. D.-A. Jurado, M. Z. Suárez, and R. M. A. Valdés, "Prediction of air traffic complexity through a dynamic complexity indicator and machine learning models," *Journal of Air Transport Management*, vol. 119, p. 102632, 2024.